

THE EFFECT OF CLASSICAL GUIDANCE SERVICES AND INDIVIDUAL SERVICES ON STUDENTS MOTIVATION TO CONTINUE TO COLLEGE

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Abstract

This research aimed to determine the measurement of the influence of classical tutoring services and individual services on guidance and counseling (BK) teaching methods in high schools in providing motivation for students to continue their education to college. The research method was carried out through distributing research questionnaires about classical services, individual services on student motivation. After the questionnaire results were collected and tabulated, analysis was then carried out using the multiple regression analysis method using SPSS 20. The research results revealed that classical services and individual services partially (together) had an influence on student motivation with a large influence. Still in the weak interval, with the classical service variable not having a significant influence.

Keywords: classical services, individual services, student motivation, extrinsic factors

INTRODUCTION

The increasing complex challenges of the future, as well as responding to problems in the development of world progress in the era of industrial revolution 5.0, require hard, intelligent and capable efforts for every individual, especially for young people who are still at the educational level. Technological developments in the era of globalization cause educational institutions to achieve cultural, strategic and operational changes (Dewi et al., 2020).

Educational institutions must strive for changes that are relevant to the preparation needs and learning processes of 21st century students to achieve quality graduates who are competent in filling national and even international career opportunities (Carvalho & Santos 2021; Mosteanu, 2020; Arpan et al., 2022; Darma, 2020; Adesote, 2022).

One of them is changing your mindset

and perspective in motivating yourself to continue improving your individual abilities, both in the form of soft skills and hard skills. In the current era, many high school graduates decide not to continue their education to college, some choose to work or are even unemployed.

There are many factors that cause students to decide not to continue or continue their education to higher education, including extrinsic and intrinsic factors (Vulperhorst et al., 2021; Fathoni et al, 2017; Baker, 2019; Nieuwoudt & Pedler, 2023; Wan, 2021; Busher & James, 2019). The benchmark for achieving the desired university education requires a motivational boost or desire within students by considering soft skills (inner abilities) and the availability of supportive learning facilities.

Motivation is an urge that arises in a person consciously or unconsciously to carry out an action with a certain goal or efforts that can cause a person or certain group of people to be moved

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to do something because they want to achieve the desired goal or get satisfaction with their actions. This idea of movement is reflected in common sense ideas about motivation, such as something that makes oneself start doing a task, keeps oneself doing it, and helps oneself in completing it. Meanwhile, motives cannot be observed directly, but can be interpreted in behavior, in the form of stimulation, encouragement, or generating energy for the emergence of a certain behavior (Uno, 2007).

Motivation can grow because of the need for what is desired, both for the present and the future. Someone who has intrinsic motivation always wants to progress in learning (Djamarah, 2002). This desire is motivated by positive thinking, that all the knowledge learned will be needed and very useful now and in the future. Motivation arises because one needs something from what one has learned (Djamarah, 2002). Motivation is related to a person's needs which give rise to awareness to carry out learning activities.

Motivation to learn can come from oneself or other people such as parents, educators or teachers as well as friends and motivation can arise because of the need to learn (Dewi, 2018; Arpan & Marpanaji, 2015; Chowkase et al., 2022; Kamaruddin et al., 2023; Lestari et al., 2019). Someone who has motivation to learn will feel enthusiastic and happy when studying, but someone who has low motivation to learn will feel bored when studying.

Motivation to learn is a driving force for students to succeed and participate in activities and it all depends on the effort and abilities they have. Therefore, if the student does not have the motivation to learn, he will be lazy about listening and paying attention to the lessons delivered by the teacher in front of the class. Unlike those who have higher learning motivation, they will be more diligent and always listen to what their teacher says during the learning process.

Therefore, providing the right motivation will really support the enthusiasm for learning and encourage students to achieve well and optimally. One of the efforts made by teachers to increase students' learning motivation is by giving awards or prizes to students who succeed in achieving high achievements.

The classical tutoring service is an effective service for identifying extra student needs which can help in providing service according to needs (Farozin, 2019). Classical guidance services are guidance services provided by educators or counselors to a group of students or counselors which are carried out in class face-to-face. In general, classical guidance is carried out by means of lectures. However, the lecture method is sometimes less effective and makes students less interested.

Therefore, educators or counselors must be creative in choosing implementation methods. Educators or counselors can use media such as audio-visual or others to support the guidance implementation process (Ghufron et al., 2022). The use of media can also be adjusted to the facilities and infrastructure available at the school.

Apart from classical guidance services, there are services that can also be a determinant for increasing students' self-motivation, namely individual guidance services, which are services provided by guidance and counseling teachers individually or individually. Individual counseling services are one of the many forms of "guidance services".

This service is even said to be the most important service of all existing forms of guidance services. Individual counseling services are the key to all guidance and counseling activities. Because if you master the techniques of individual counseling services, it will be easier to carry out other guidance and counseling processes. Therefore, prospective counselors are advised to master the processes and techniques of individual counseling.

Previous research result showed that 34 students observed and the motivation scores were low, so individual counseling was carried out with behavioral strategies using modeling techniques to produce changes in the students' attitudes which were able to follow the teaching and learning process well and have increased self-motivation. Based on these problems, this research aimed to determine the effect of classical services and individual services as teaching methods for guidance and counseling teachers in schools on student motivation.

METHOD

In this research, the analytical method used

was the regression analysis method to explain the relationship and influence between variables. Regression analysis is a statistical method that functions to test the extent of the causal relationship between variables, regression analysis is used to find out how the dependent (dependent) variable can be predicted through variables.

Independent partially or jointly, the types of regression analysis that can be used are simple regression (linear regression) and multiple regression. Multiple regression analysis is used in research because there is more than one independent variable in testing the dependent variable, this multiple analysis is a tool for testing the value of the dependent variable if there is an independent variable (Usman & Setiady, 2011).

The data in this research used primary data. Primary data is a source of data obtained directly from original sources (not through intermediary media). In this case, primary data was obtained from the results questionnaire which was distributed to students of SMA Negeri 1 Pulau Punjung class XII, with criteria questionnaire as follows 1) The questionnaires are grouped into four variables, with 3 variables independent (classical services and individual services) in measuring the dependent variable (student motivation), 2) The questionnaires had statement items as indicator in measuring the level of each variable, 3) The specified questionnaires were created in Google Form as a tool for distribution to students.

After the questionnaires have been collected, they will be tabulated using Microsoft Excel, then the tabulated data measured for analysis using SPSS 20. Apart from distributing questionnaires in analyzing level dependent variable, it is also reviewed literature as material in analysis variable dependent was started mainly by national studies or educational journals that had samples from Indonesia. In this context, the database was searched with the keywords “Classical Services, Services Individuals and Student Motivation” with data appearing as many as 16,900 keywords that appeared in Google Scholar searches in a collection of articles from 2012 to 2023.

After this literature review, all research was checked one by one for suitability with the

research criteria, namely student motivation in continuing to college or student motivation in studying. Next, the articles are grouped with the aim of seeing their relationship to the research to be conducted.

The research instrument was to collect data about classical services and individual services, as well as Student Motivation. To test a hypothesis, correct, careful and accurate data is needed because the validity of the results of hypothesis testing depends on the truth and accuracy of the data. Meanwhile, the truth and accuracy of the data obtained depends on the data collection tool used (instrument) as the data source. This research used a questionnaire trial which is expected to be a research measuring tool used to reach the truth or approach the truth.

From this questionnaire it is hoped that the main data related to the problem can be solved. The questionnaire used Likert Scale measurements (Likert, 1931). With this Likert scale, respondents are asked to complete a questionnaire that requires them to indicate their level of agreement with a series of questions. The questions or statements used in this research are usually called research variables and are specifically determined by the researcher (Sugiyono, 2013).

The data processing method in this research is using SPSS version 20.0 software. Data analysis in this research includes multiple linear regression, descriptive analysis, analysis, validity test, test reliability. By using multiple linear regression analysis techniques or Ordinary Least Square (OLS). Multiple linear regression analysis aimed to explain the magnitude of the influence of classical services and individual services on student motivation. The general linear regression equation for testing the hypotheses in this research showed in formula (1).

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + e \quad (1)$$

Y = Student Motivation

a = Constanta Coefficient

b = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Classical Service

X2 = Individual Service

E = Error, nuisance variable

To measure the level of or big influence variable independent to variable depend use interval coefficient regression showed in Table 1.

Table 1 Interval Coefficient Regression

Interval	Information
≥ 80,00%	Very strong
60,00% - 79,99%	Strong
40,00% - 59,99%	Strong enough
20,00% - 39,99%	Weak
≤ 19,99%	Very weak

Descriptive analysis was statistics used to analyze data by describing or illustrating the data that has been collected as it is without intending to make generally accepted conclusions or generalizations (Sugiyono, 2013). Descriptive analysis includes presenting data with tables, graphs, diagrams circle, pictogram, calculation of mean, maximum and minimum. This analysis was not carried out significantly and there was no error level because it was not intended to make generalizations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted to analyze classical services, individual services on students' motivation to continue to higher education. For this reason, a description of the research data related to the results of statistical processing using SPSS 20. The test of the validity of each questionnaires statement item distributed using the calculated r value which must be greater than the r table value.

Table 2 Validity Test of Classical Services

		Correlations								
		X.1.1	X.1.2	X.1.3	X.1.4	X.1.5	X.1.6	X.1.7	X.1.8	Total_X.1
X.1.1	Pearson Correlation	1	.352 ^{**}	.511 ^{**}	.499 ^{**}	.444 ^{**}	.429 ^{**}	.522 ^{**}	.586 ^{**}	.720 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
X.1.2	Pearson Correlation	.352 ^{**}	1	.408 ^{**}	.096	.152	.238 [*]	.157	.170	.483 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000	.431	.212	.049	.197	.164	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
X.1.3	Pearson Correlation	.511 ^{**}	.408 ^{**}	1	.258 [*]	.369 ^{**}	.288 [*]	.448 ^{**}	.425 ^{**}	.630 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.032	.002	.016	.000	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
X.1.4	Pearson Correlation	.499 ^{**}	.096	.258 [*]	1	.813 ^{**}	.668 ^{**}	.680 ^{**}	.667 ^{**}	.775 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)					.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
X.1.5	Pearson Correlation	.444 ^{**}	.152	.369 ^{**}	.813 ^{**}	1	.537 ^{**}	.690 ^{**}	.611 ^{**}	.764 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)						.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
X.1.6	Pearson Correlation	.429 ^{**}	.238 [*]	.288 [*]	.668 ^{**}	.537 ^{**}	1	.769 ^{**}	.762 ^{**}	.800 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)							.000	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
X.1.7	Pearson Correlation	.522 ^{**}	.157	.448 ^{**}	.680 ^{**}	.690 ^{**}	.769 ^{**}	1	.872 ^{**}	.863 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)								.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
X.1.8	Pearson Correlation	.586 ^{**}	.170	.425 ^{**}	.667 ^{**}	.611 ^{**}	.762 ^{**}	.872 ^{**}	1	.857 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)									.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
Total_X.1	Pearson Correlation	.720 ^{**}	.483 ^{**}	.630 ^{**}	.775 ^{**}	.764 ^{**}	.800 ^{**}	.863 ^{**}	.857 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)									.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 showed that the calculated r (correlation coefficient value) for the classical service components X.1.1 to X.1.8 > r table 0,2369, then the decision was made using the significance level or $\alpha = 5\%$, the existing questionnaire was **VALID**, then we can use all of it in further testing.

Table 3 Validity Test of Individual Services

		Correlations			
		X.2.1	X.2.2	X.2.3	Total_X.2
X.2.1	Pearson Correlation	1	.806 ^{**}	.704 ^{**}	.919 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69
X.2.2	Pearson Correlation	.806 ^{**}	1	.655 ^{**}	.898 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69
X.2.3	Pearson Correlation	.704 ^{**}	.655 ^{**}	1	.889 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.000
	N	69	69	69	69
Total_X.2	Pearson Correlation	.919 ^{**}	.898 ^{**}	.889 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.000
	N	69	69	69	69

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 showed that the calculated r (correlation coefficient value) for individual service components X.2.1 to X.1.3 > r table 0,2369, then the decision was made using the significance level or $\alpha = 5\%$, the existing questionnaire was **VALID**, then we can use all of it in further testing.

Table 4 Motivation Validity Test

		Correlations					
		Y.1	Y.2	Y.3	Y.4	Y.5	Total_Y
Y.1	Pearson Correlation	1	.520 ^{**}	.581 ^{**}	.419 ^{**}	.459 ^{**}	.775 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69
Y.2	Pearson Correlation	.520 ^{**}	1	.809 ^{**}	.466 ^{**}	.614 ^{**}	.849 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69
Y.3	Pearson Correlation	.581 ^{**}	.809 ^{**}	1	.332 ^{**}	.787 ^{**}	.857 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.005	.000	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69
Y.4	Pearson Correlation	.419 ^{**}	.466 ^{**}	.332 ^{**}	1	.293 [*]	.690 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)					.014	.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69
Y.5	Pearson Correlation	.459 ^{**}	.614 ^{**}	.787 ^{**}	.293 [*]	1	.760 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)						.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69
Total_Y	Pearson Correlation	.775 ^{**}	.849 ^{**}	.857 ^{**}	.690 ^{**}	.760 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)						.000
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 showed that the calculated r (correlation coefficient value) for the student motivation component Y.1 to Y.5 > r table 0,2369, so the decision was to use a significance level or $\alpha = 5\%$, the existing questionnaire was **VALID**, then we can use all of it in further testing.

Apart from the validity test, a reliability test was also carried out, namely a variable consistency test by measuring the Cronbach's alpha value using the calculated r value which must be greater than the r table value.

Table 5 Classical Service Reliability Test

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.866	8

Table 5 showed that the calculated r (correlation coefficient value) for the classical service component (X.1) with the number of items 8 was $0.866 > r$ table 0.2369, so the decision was to use a significance level or $\alpha = 5\%$. If these variables are declared reliable or consistent, then we can use all of them in further testing.

Table 6 Individual Service Reliability Test

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.878	3

Table 6 showed that the calculated r (correlation coefficient value) for the individual service component (X.2) with the number of items 3 was $0.878 > r$ table 0.2369, so the decision was to use a significance level or $\alpha = 5\%$. If these variables are declared reliable or consistent, then we can use all of them in further testing.

Table 7 Reliability Test of Student Motivation

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.827	5

Table 7 showed that the calculated r (correlation coefficient value) for the student motivation component (Y) with the number of items 5 was $0.827 > r$ table 0.2369, so the decision was to use the significance level or $\alpha = 5\%$, for this variable declared reliable or consistent, then we can use all of it in further testing.

The analysis used to determine the relationship between the variables studied will use a multiple regression analysis test with 2 independent variables, the test results can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8 The Influence of Classical Services and Individual Services on Student Motivation

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.626 ^a	.392	.373	2.427

a. Predictors: (Constant), Total_X.2, Total_X.1

Table 8 showed the values analyzed for multiple linear regression analysis were *adjusted r square*. Earned value *adjusted r square* amounting to 0.373, meaning that the contribution of the independent variables in influencing the dependent variable was 37.3%, while the remaining 62.7% was influenced by other variables.

Table 9 ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	250.274	2	125.137	21.238	.000 ^b
Residual	388.885	66	5.892		
Total	639.159	68			

a. Dependent Variable: Total_Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), Total_X.2, Total_X.1

Table 9 showed that the tests can be analyzed simultaneously. A sig value of 0.000 was obtained, meaning that there was a simultaneous influence of X1 and X2 on Y or the fit of the research model.

Table 10 Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	6.648	2.238		2.971	.004
1 Total_X.1	.311	.090	.447	3.453	.001
Total_X.2	.310	.174	.231	1.784	.079

a. Dependent Variable: Total_Y

Table 10 showed that the variables X1 and X2 in column B, as well as the sig value variable X1 and X2 obtained the following regression equation in formula (2).

$$Y = 6.648 + 0.311X1 + 0.310X2 \quad (2)$$

The constant value obtained was 6.648, meaning that statistically without the presence of X1 and X2, the value of Y was 6.648. The coefficient value for the variable X1 was obtained at 0.311 meaning that the influence of X1 to Y was because it had a percentage of 31.10%. Next, the coefficient value for variable X2 was obtained 0.310. This means that the magnitude of the influence of X2 on Y was also weak because it had a percentage of 31.00%.

The coefficient value for the variable X1

was positive, meaning that X1 had a positive effect on Y, the higher X1, the higher Y was and vice versa. The coefficient value for the variable X2 was positive, meaning that X2 had a positive effect on Y, the higher X2, the higher Y was and vice versa.

The sig value of variable X1 was obtained 0,001 smaller than alpha 0.05 so H_0 was rejected, meaning there was a significant influence of X1 on Y, but the sig value was variable X2 in amount of 0.079 bigger than alpha 0.05 so H_0 accepted, meaning there was no significant influence of X2 on Y.

CONCLUSION

The analysis test results obtained in this research showed that classical services and individual services have an influence on student motivation but the influence given to weak intervals and individual service variables did not have a significant influence. So it is necessary for guidance and counseling teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Pulau Punjung to look for other methods or models of guidance to increase students' motivation to continue to college. Apart from finding other methods and models of guidance, it is also necessary to look at other variables that are taken into consideration by guidance and counseling teachers in increasing their students' motivation, because the percentage influence of classical services and individual services only has an influence of 32%, there are still many other variables that have not been studied.

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